

Perhitungan Jumlah Angkutan Umum Optimal Dengan Simulasi Berbasis Agen

Ary Setijadi Prihatmanto (Bandung Institute of Technology), Agus Sukoco (Bandar Lampung University), Dr. Rahadian Yusuf (Bandung Institute of Technology), Dr. Reza Darmakusuma (Bandung Institute of Technology), Vitradisa Pratama (Mayasari Bakti University), Dr. Agus Budiono (Bandung Institute of Technology)

Email:itb.ac.id@gmail.com

Abstract. Use 10 pt Times font for the body text with one/single line spacing, and 12 pt spacing for the next heading. Left and right indent 0.5cm. Maximum length **200 words**.

Keywords: use 10 pt; lower case; italic; Times; write alphabetically in **5-10 words**.

1 Introduction

For this section title use 12 pt, bold, Times, title case with 6 pt spacing to the body text. Use 11 pt Times for the body text with **1 (one) line spacing** between lines, 12 pt spacing between paragraph and 18 pt spacing for the next heading.¹ To set the style in whole manuscript, simply use this template and follow the instructions on Section 2.

2 Page Layout, Style and Formatting

For this template use the custom margin in **Page Layout** menu: Top and Left margin are 4 cm, Bottom is 6.5 cm and Right is 4.5 cm. Gutter position is Left. Orientation page is Portrait.

The styles used in this paper are:

1. **Title**, for paper's title
2. **Author**, for author's name
3. **Address**, for author's address
4. **Abstract**, for abstract
5. **Heading 1**, for section title
6. **Heading 2**, for sub section title
7. **Heading 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9** for the next sub ... sub-section title

8. **Text**, for body text
9. **Equation** and **Enumeration**
10. **Figure**, for figure caption
11. **Table**, for table caption
12. **Reference**, for references
13. **Acknowledge**, for References and Acknowledgement header.

This template is already set for the paper in *style and formatting*, so you can use those styles by typing the style name in the **Style** box as shown in the figure below:

2.1 Mathematical Formulation

Equations should be typed with indent 1.27 pt, and numbered consecutively starting with (1) set flush right. To set the style, type ***Equation*** in the **Style** box, or from **Style Menu**. But this style only sets the tab stop position. To put the equation to the right just press the **Tab** button one time. And to type the equation number, press the **Tab** button once again from the right side of the equation.

$$x^2 + y^2 = z^2 \tag{1}$$

For numbering, use ordered numbers (1), (2), (3), and so on. Do not order by Chapter i.e (1.1), (1,2), (1,3). For referring an Equation in the body text, please use “Eq. (1)”.

2.1.1 Section and Sub-section Title

Just type *Heading 1* for section title, *Heading 2* for sub section title, and *Heading 3* for sub sub-section title. The number will set automatically.

2.1.2 Figures and Tables

All figures and tables should be centered and numbered consecutively. **Use the Figure and Table Style for every description of a figure and table respectively**

Figure 1 Type *Figure* in the style box. The caption should be typed in lower case. Choose *center* if the caption fit on one line.

Table 1 Summary of physical parameters.

No	Segments	Length (km)	Elevation (meter)
1	A-B	25	30
2	B-C	75.15	10
3	C-D	44.75	50
4	D-E	72.5	10
5	E-F	21.25	10

3 Length

The maximum length of article is **15 pages**, including all pictures, tables, nomenclature, references, etc.

4 Nomenclature (if necessary)

List the nomenclature in alphabetical order. List Roman letters followed by Greek symbols followed by subscript and superscripts.

A	=	Amplitude
C_d	=	drag coefficient
f_e	=	linearization coefficient
K_i	=	modification factor
γ	=	wave number
ψ	=	Complex wave number

5 References

Within the text, references should be cited by giving the last name of the author(s) and numbered consecutively starting with [1], i.e:

“Some results from the experiment were given by Wijaya and Riyanto in [1], Wijaya, *et.al* in [2], Majerski and Przybylo in [3], Nurdin, *et al.* in [4] and [5].”

Note that in the case of three or more authors, only the last name of the first author is cited and the others are denoted by *et al.* **The same rule is also held for the header title on even pages (see Header in top of Page 2).**

Within the Reference chapter, use the same typeface as the body of the text for the references, or just find *Reference* in **Styles Windows**. In References chapter you should write based on the order of appearances, not alphabetically. Example of References:

References

- [1] Sutasurya, L.A. & Riyanto, B., *Title of Paper*, Name of Journal, **8**(1), pp. 20-25, Dec. 2005. (Journal)
- [2] Sutasurya, L.A., Handojo, A. & Riyanto, B., *Title of book*, ed. 2, Publisher, 2007. (Book)
- [3] Williams, J., *Name of Paper*, Name of Book, Name of the editor(s), eds., Publisher, pp. 67-69, 2006. (Book with paper title and editor)

- [4] Suharto (ed), *Title of Paper*, Name of Proc., pp. 5-10, 2008. (Conference Proceedings)
- [5] Name of the author(s), *Title of paper* (if available), Organization, URL Link, (1 April 2011). (URL Link)
- [6] Nicole, R., *Title of Paper*, Name of Journal, submitted for publication. (Pending publication)
- [7] John, K., *Title of Paper*, unpublished. (Unpublished manuscript)
- [8] Rashid, L., *Title of Dissertation*, PhD dissertation, Name of Dept., Name of Univ., City, 2010. (Thesis or Dissertation)
- [9] Jenny, P., Name of Institution, City, personal communication, 2010. (Personal communication)
- [10] Name of the author(s), *Title of Technical Report*, Technical Report TR-0334 (34-56), Name of Institution, City, Dec. 2009. (Technical report with report number)
- [11] Name of the author(s), *Title of Paper in English*, Name of Journal, **8**(4), pp. 20-25, 2010. (Text in Indonesian and Abstract in English) (Use this if the references in other language than English).

6 Manuscript Content

The contents of the paper should be in the following order:

1. Title of Paper
2. Author names and affiliation
3. Abstract
4. Body of the text (Introduction Conclusion)
5. Acknowledgements
6. Nomenclature
7. References

Acknowledgement

If necessary you can type your acknowledgement here.

Title in Odd Page Header

Shorten the title of paper to a maximum of 50 characters from the full title to appears in every **header of odd pages**, use 11 pt size Century Gothic font.